

IMMUNE PROTECTION INDICATORS IN ATHLETES

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the health of people involved in high-performance and elite sports is of particular concern. Regular, intense physical activity causes changes in the human body, affecting most organs and systems, as well as fundamental biological processes. Research conducted in our country and abroad in recent decades shows that poor health and reduced athletic performance in athletes are associated with defects in nonspecific resistance and immune defense. Furthermore, the harmonious functioning of the immune system depends on the normal functioning of other organs and systems, so any disruption inevitably affects the athlete's immune status. Excessive training and competitive stress in athletes can lead to immunodeficiency and autoaggressive conditions. Long-term irritants that exceed the body's response thresholds lead to premorbid conditions, various disorders, and exhaustion. The period of increased susceptibility of the body to infections in elite athletes after acute and significant physical exertion is called the "open window." The "open window" theory links the surge in illness among athletes to short-term suppression of the immune system due to excessive physical exertion.

Decreased immunity is an early symptom of impaired adaptation in an athlete's body and is accompanied by a decline in anti-infective defenses, decreased phagocytosis and leukocyte migration, and a decrease in the number of eosinophils and lymphocytes in the blood. Immunosuppression during periods of intense training is multifactorial. Significant overloads in athletes are accompanied by changes in hormonal status and biochemical shifts that can affect the functioning of the immune system. At the same time, physical exertion and stressful situations during sports can also play an immunopotentiating role, optimizing the adaptive processes of other organs and systems. However, despite a significant number of publications on immunological changes, it can hardly be claimed that their nature and significance have been sufficiently studied. It is known that acute fatigue is accompanied by weakness and decreased

performance, and overexertion, along with this, disruption of the cardiovascular system and other organs and systems. Overtraining also causes autonomic changes, disruptions in the central nervous and endocrine systems, and unstable athletic performance. In most cases, fatigue, overexertion, and overtraining are assessed based on rather subjective indicators. There are some indications that these processes are independent of stress levels. There is still no consensus on what constitutes reliable markers of overtraining. Data linking them to changes in objective immunological parameters are limited.

The aim of the study was to assess the state of immune homeostasis in highly qualified athletes under intense physical and emotional stress, and to develop and substantiate a concept and mathematical model of homeostatic shifts during overexertion and overtraining of athletes.

The object of the study is highly qualified athletes of various sports specializations, members of national teams.

The subject of the study is indicators of endocrine, biochemical and immune status in the regulation of homeostasis in highly qualified athletes at various stages of preparation for domestic competitions.

Research objectives

1. To assess the state of humoral and cellular immunity in highly qualified athletes using a range of immunological methods.

2. To analyze the impact of physical and psycho-emotional stress on the immune system of athletes at different periods of the training cycle.

Research results. The most important issue in modern high-performance sport is improving the structure of the training process across macrocycles, periods, stages, and microcycles of preparation. Modern training design is based on studying the mechanisms of long-term stable adaptation. As the body's adaptability increases, specific changes occur that allow for the unleashing of optimal reserves in activity and a reduction in stress during physiological rest. Moreover, each athlete has their own threshold level of physical exertion intensity. Therefore, fundamentally new information approaches to modern technologies of progressive, anticipatory training are needed, as well as the development of modern methods for monitoring athletes' condition at all stages of the training cycle, to identify pathological, and possibly pre-pathological, conditions in order to promptly correct any detected disturbances and maintain the athlete's high functional capabilities. A set of new data has been obtained on the nature of immune shifts in the innate and acquired immune systems of highly qualified athletes during homeostasis disruptions under the influence of physical and psychological stress of varying intensity and focus.

A comprehensive analysis of immune and biochemical changes during the macrocycle of training for highly qualified gymnasts competing in high-stakes international competitions was conducted. For the first time, a link was established between biochemical and immunological parameters and the level of physical and psycho-emotional stress at various stages of the training cycle.

First, most authors present data assessing a limited number of nonspecific defense and immune responses. Information on the status of any broad range of indicators is usually lacking. Meanwhile, it is known that suppression of individual immune defense mechanisms often has no impact on the overall resistance of the body. Numerous studies have shown that immune deficiency is often caused by an imbalance in the interconnections within the immune system,

altering the number, direction, and intensity of statistical relationships between immunological indicators, and these mechanisms have been insufficiently studied in athletes. Second, there is insufficient clarity regarding the mechanisms underlying impairments in nonspecific resistance and immunity (innate immune responses) during sports. Information on the quantitative relationships between the intensities of stress and immunological responses is often absent from publications on this topic. When examining immunological disorders in athletes, the role of fatigue, overwork, overexertion, and overtraining is often overlooked.

For the first time, the characteristics of the immune and biochemical profile of overtraining syndrome in athletes have been scientifically substantiated.

For the first time, the importance of endogenous intoxication, determined by objective immune and biochemical markers, in the development of the pathological condition of overtraining in athletes has been demonstrated. The role of cortisol in changing immunological parameters and athletes' adaptation to physical activity has been determined.

Based on correlation analysis and the Pleiades method, a modern homeostasis model has been developed that reflects the dynamics of intersystemic connections in the body of a highly skilled athlete during the transition from fatigue to pathological overtraining. For the first time, an animal experiment has identified morphological changes in the central (thymus) and peripheral (lymph nodes) immune organs and endocrine glands (adrenal glands, testes) during physical and psychoemotional stress. A new concept has been formulated regarding the role of endocrine, biochemical, and immune status in regulating homeostasis in highly skilled athletes, ensuring physical fitness and high performance, and outlining ways and methods for correcting homeostatic imbalances.

As a result of the conducted studies, the role of cellular non-specific and specific immunological indicators in the suppression of immune defense, disruption of homeostasis and increased morbidity in highly qualified athletes was established, which is of interest for immunology and human physiology.

Based on a study of depressive and potentiating changes in the immune system of athletes under physical stress, compensatory mechanisms for maintaining homeostasis were deciphered and critical points for correction were identified. The relationships between immune system parameters and physical and psychoemotional stress in athletes were studied, revealing new mechanisms for the development of immunodeficiency states, which has theoretical significance for sports physiology and medicine, as well as theoretical immunology.

The data obtained from the study on the relationship between increased cortisol levels in athletes and immune system parameters allows us to evaluate the role of cortisol in both immune reactivity disorders and the formation of protective reactions aimed at adapting the body to physical activity.

The conducted studies, based on the established specific changes in immune and biochemical parameters during different periods of the training cycle, allow for the optimization of the training process to achieve higher athletic results with minimal impact on athletes' health. The use of the proposed methods for monitoring biochemical and immunological parameters enables the early detection of pre-pathological and pathological conditions in athletes, allowing for the timely correction of any detected disorders and the maintenance of high functional capabilities.

The results of the analysis of immune and biochemical changes in different periods of the training cycle will allow us to identify the mechanisms of adaptation failure during the competitive period and demonstrate the importance of timely recovery measures during the transition period for maintaining the health of athletes.

A dynamic study of a group of gymnasts demonstrated the importance of a methodically correct macrocycle of preparation for major competitions in preventing immune disorders in athletes. The suppression of certain immune system parameters that occurs under intense physical exertion is offset by an increase in other indicators of immunological reactivity.

Conclusions. One of the main reasons for the increased incidence of colds and infectious diseases in athletes is a decreased level of one of the protective humoral factors of the innate immune system - salivary lysozyme, which is most pronounced in athletes with overtraining syndrome. Under the influence of high-intensity physical activity, athletes develop T-cell deficiency: the number of T-lymphocytes and their subpopulations decreases, signs of activation of immunocompetent cells appear - an increase in the number of CD25⁺ and CD95⁺ lymphocytes and an increase in spontaneous proliferative activity of lymphocytes, which indicates activation of the immune system, and an increase in the number of CD95⁺ lymphocytes - an increase in the body's readiness for physiologically programmed death of immunocompetent cells - apoptosis; the ability of T-lymphocytes to be activated by mitogens decreases. At the same time, activation of the B-immune system occurs: the content of B-lymphocytes in the blood increases and the response to stimulation with B-mitogen in vitro increases, and the levels of immunoglobulins in the blood and saliva increase.

The greatest changes in the immune system of athletes are observed against a background of elevated cortisol levels and a decrease in the anabolic index, which reflects the prevalence of catabolic processes in the body and indicates a pathological state of overtraining. The greatest changes in immune status are observed during the competitive period of the training cycle, and during the recovery period, with rational adaptation, these changes are fully restored.

An increase in the level of endogenous intoxication in athletes under conditions of high training and competitive loads indicates inadequacy of loads and a violation of optimal adaptation, requiring correction of the training process.

Immunomorphological studies in experimental animals reveal the causes of immune and metabolic disorders during physical overexertion and stress: pronounced changes in the morphology of the central (thymus) and peripheral (lymph nodes) organs of the immune system and significant atrophy of the endocrine organs are observed.

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